

Constrained Nested Optimization of a BaZrS₃/CIGS Two-Terminal Tandem Solar Cell Using SCAPS-1D with Surrogate-Guided Current Matching

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Abstract— A numerical framework is presented for a two-terminal (2T) monolithic BaZrS₃/CIGS tandem solar cell in SCAPS-1D. A constrained nested optimization couples a current-matching loop, which adjusts the top-absorber thickness by Brent root finding, with a surrogate model and a feasibility classifier. The analysis extends beyond ideal simulation assumptions to capture more realistic device behaviour expected in practical tandem solar cell operation. The optimized device reaches a power conversion efficiency of 30.33 % Voc of 2.15 V, Jsc of 17.97 mA/cm², and FF of 78 %, while current matching at a top and a bottom thickness, where the optimal top absorber thickness is 379.9 nm.

Keywords— BaZrS₃, CIGS, tandem solar cell, SCAPS-1D, current matching, Brent loop

I. INTRODUCTION

Tandem solar cells stack wide- and low-bandgap absorbers to capture a broader solar spectrum. In a 2T monolithic device the series-connected sub-cells add their voltages while current is limited by the smaller sub-cell, demanding current matching.

BaZrS₃ (1.70 eV) [1], a stable earth-abundant chalcogenide perovskite, pairs well with mature CIGS (1.10 eV). This work integrates current matching, surrogate-guided optimization, and full-tandem parasitic-thermal analysis.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Device Setup

The top sub-cell uses the sequence FTO / SnO₂ (ETL) BaZrS₃ (absorber) / CuSbS₂ (HTL); the bottom sub-cell uses ZnO:Al / ZnO / CdS / CIGS (absorber) [2], as shown in **Figure 1**.

B. Simulation and Optimization Framework

SCAPS-1D simulations under AM1.5G were automated by Python script, which generated filtered spectra, simulated both sub-cells, series-combined I–V curves, and optimized tandem performance through current matching, Gaussian-process surrogate modelling, and feasibility-guided exploration of eight parameters.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The wide-bandgap BaZrS₃ top cell absorbs the short-wavelength photons, transmitting the remaining spectrum to the CIGS bottom cell for long-wavelength collection. As the short-circuit current is limited by the available photon budget, the efficiency enhancement mainly results from increased open-circuit voltage (2.07–2.15 V) and fill factor due to reduced recombination in the bottom sub-cell. Current matching is obtained at the optimal top and bottom absorber thickness by Brent loop matched currents, raising tandem efficiency from 30.33 %.

Figure 1. proposed BaZrS₃/CIGS 2T tandem device structure

The top cell exhibits a strong spectral response in the short-wavelength region up to its band edge near 729 nm, whereas the CIGS bottom cell collects across an extended range to approximately 1100 nm. The complementary spectral absorption of the two sub cells enables effective current matching, with both the top and bottom cells delivering a photocurrent density of approximately 17.9 mA/cm², thereby minimizing current loss and enhancing the tandem device performance.

IV. CONCLUSION

This work confirms the strong potential of the BaZrS₃/CIGS tandem architecture and identifies the dominant loss mechanisms governing its operation. The obtained results provide a theoretical performance benchmark for the proposed device under optimized SCAPS 1D simulation conditions, establishing a foundation for future experimental validation and practical device development. Future efforts should address realistic optical reflection, expand the parameter sensitivity analysis, and pursue device fabrication to validate the predicted performance under operating conditions.

References

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